

STUDENTS' AWARENESS AND READINESS TOWARDS UTILIZATION OF SOCIAL MEDIA FOR BIOLOGY EDUCATION IN PUBLIC UNIVERSITIES IN NIGER STATE

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ABSTRACT There are several benefits when Biology students in public universities are taught using social media in their classrooms, these benefits include: students will have better engagement, improved learning experiences and interactions among the students. This study investigates the students' awareness and readiness towards utilization of social media for biology education in public universities in Niger State. Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. Two research questions were raised and two null hypotheses, randomly sample of 120 (males = 73 and female = 47) biology education students in universities in Niger State was used for this study. Instrument used to gather data was Awareness and Readiness Social Media Biology Questionnaire (ARSOMEQBQ) was used for data collection. Data collected was analyzed using mean and standard deviation while ANOVA was used to test the two null hypotheses that were formulated. The findings of the study indicated that there was no significant difference in the mean male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State. Also, there was no significant difference in the readiness of male and female universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended that social media should be used as a tool in universities in Niger State for biology instructional delivery in order to act as supplementary teaching and learning materials. Also, both male and female biology education students should be motivated in order to make use of social media for instructional delivery in their academic activities.

KEYWORDS: Social Media, Awareness, Readiness, Biology and Technology

I. INTRODUCTION

The digital revolution has arguably transformed every area of human discipline. The revolution did not spare education, rather, it has brought a radical change into how knowledge is created, generated, communicated, stored and used. Historically speaking, the term technology in science can be traced back to the earliest time when crude materials like stones, leaves, animal skin and paintings on walls were used as method of sharing knowledge (Nsofor & Bello, 2015). Technology plays a vital role in wealth creation, improvement in the quality of life and real economic growth and transformation in any society; it is also a gateway to scientific and technological greatness of any nation (Anunobi, 2012). Education is a systematic process through which an individual acquires knowledge, experience, skills and good behavior in pursuit of life activities. Similarly, Technology is a body of knowledge that is applied in creating tools, building of skills and extracting or collecting materials (Nsofor & Bello, 2015). Education is the act of imparting or acquiring general knowledge, developing the powers of reasoning and judgment, and generally preparing one-self intellectually for mature life, which can also be acquire through biology.

Biology can be seen as the laws and phenomenon relating to an organism or group of organisms. The study of biology employs activities such as identification of problem, observations, experimentation, data collection and analysis. The science of biology has been divided into many sub disciplines such as Botany, Bacteriology, Anatomy, Zoology, Histology, Mycology, Embryology, Parasitology, Genetics, Molecular Biology, Systematic, Immunology, Microbiology, Physiology, Cell-Biology, Cytology, Ecology, and

Virology. Other branches of science that include part of biology comprises of Paleontology, taxonomy, evolution, Phycology, Helimentology, Protozoology, Entomology, Biochemistry, Biophysics, Biomathematics, Bioengineering, Bioclimatology, and anthropology (Micheal., Henry., Franklin., & Fidelis, 2016). Biology education is the study that combines knowledge of biology with the pedagogy for the purpose of equipping learners with relevant knowledge and skills for manpower enhancement (Micheal., Henry., Franklin., & Fidelis, 2016). The main focus is to produce qualified and competent biology students in various fields of endeavor; to cover areas of specialization like medicine, pharmacy, Nursing, Physiology, Biochemistry, and Biological sciences. This is in accordance with (Umake & Nwafor, 2014) who opined that the major objectives of Biology education include to produce qualified graduate teachers with requisite competence and skills in teaching biology, and produce teachers who teach their students how to discover new things especially as it concerns life sciences and sustainable environment. It also aims to provide teachers and graduates with general education that can help them understand and face the challenging world of science and information technology which could probably improve through the use of social media.

Social media network is an online service platforms or site that focuses on building, reflecting of social relations among people who share interest and activities. Most media technologies include blogs, business networks, enterprise social networks, forum, microblogs, and photo sharing among others (Effiong & Odey 2013). Social media is defined as a utility tool to integrate online technologies and educational learning to support and develop academia. This means that technologies used by learners, which they believe is important and supportive for their educational learning can be considered as social media. Various functions, in and outside online learning management systems, support students interactions synchronously and asynchronously. Social media is considered as a tool in education, used by more than half of the learners to enable collaboration, real-time dialogue and knowledge or data sharing (Chen & Bryer, 2012). Social media proves very effective in instruction delivery services (Rochas, 2011). Users access relevant information on every area of learning through the use of search engines such as Opera mini Google, UC Browser, Safari, Google Chrome and others. Teachers and learners are also able to Google and retrieve information at ease within minute (Zur, 2011).

Social media sites play an important role in the lives of many young people especially those in higher institution level. Over 60% of 13-17 years old have at least one profile on a social networking site, many spending more than 2 hours per day on social networking site (Sharon, 2012). The number of regular users of Social Networking Sites (SNS) has grown significantly over the last decade with a reported 73 per cent of all online adults, including 90 per cent of the 18-29 age group, in the United States using social media regularly (Duggan & Smith, 2013). One SNS in particular, Facebook, is reported to have over 1.23 billion monthly users worldwide (Ross, 2014), over 13 million users in Australia alone (Cowling, 2014) and 5,357,500 in Nigeria (Socialbakers.com). These astonishing statistics along with the rapid growth of mobile technology that includes 20.3 million mobile subscribers (ABS, 2014), raises the question of how educators can harness such a powerful and high traffic technological tool to better enhance student learning experiences and outcomes. These media technologies offer the users great opportunities to interact over the internet such as Facebook, Twitter, Skype, E-mail and instant message (2go), What Sapp (application) and others. It is a computer-mediated tool that allow people to create, share or exchange information, ideas and pictures/videos in virtual communities and network. In order to make use of social media, their need for proper awareness on the use of social media in impacting biology knowledge.

Awareness is the knowledge or understanding of a particular subject or situation, the ability to notice something using sense and also refers to someone's idea, feelings or opinions about life. Chinedu (2008) viewed awareness as the conditions of being aware and able to understand what is happening around one. In the context of this study and in agreement with the above views, awareness implies understanding, attitude and knowledge of the activities and events going on around one's environment. When one is aware of the usefulness of social media in teaching and learning of biology, there is tendency to be readiness towards using it. Readiness is one of the important variables investigated in this study and the term is defined as the state of preparedness of lecturers to meet a situation and carry out a planned sequence of

actions. Schreurs *et al.* (2008), readiness also takes account of one's capability to adapt to technological challenges, collaborative training and synchronous as well as asynchronous self-paced training". Gender is an important factor in the education. It is a composition of male and female and educational researchers, for a long time researches have shown concern on the influence of gender in the sector. Gender issue generally in education industry has become of immense importance and cannot be overlooked, but attention should be deliberately given to it, in order to make intellectual discourse free from sentiments and prejudice (Adeyinka, 2010). In the study carried out by Adediran and Kehinde (2013) who investigates gender and internet use pattern of pre-service teachers in a Nigerian College of Education. It was revealed that gender is a major factor to be considered in use of as well as feeling about the internet.

Muhammed and Okan (2018) who carried out study on the readiness levels of pre-service teachers towards mobile learning in classroom management. It was revealed that readiness level of the prospective teachers does not change depending on the gender and the students use the mobile technologies most in communication, studying, acquiring information and making plans. Venkataraman (2018) who carried out study on M-learning awareness of high school students. The result indicates that there was no significant difference in the awareness of male and female high school students on M-learning. The use of the social media is becoming an integral part of being an adolescent or young people and as a result they are communicating with themselves in an unprecedented scale. Over 60% of 13- 35 year olds have at least one profile on a social networking site, many spending more than 2 hours per day on social networking site. If social media is putting into use in educational sector, it will go a long way of improving awareness and readiness of universities students in biology education for instructional delivery. In line with this assertion, there is need to investigate the students' awareness and readiness towards utilization of social media for biology education in public universities in Niger State.

II. METHODOLOGY

The research designed adopted for this study was descriptive survey design. The population of the study comprised of all biology education university students in both Federal University of Technology Minna and Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University Lapai in Niger State, Nigeria. The target population comprised of 529 (200 Level) biology education students from FUT Minna and IBBU Lapai. 120 students were randomly selected from Federal University of Technology Minna and Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida University Lapai in Niger State Nigeria for the main study. The Instruments for the study is Awareness and Readiness Social Media Biology Questionnaire (ARSOMEQB). The ARSOMEQB comprises of 10 item questions. The questionnaire was validated by two biology education experts in Science Education Department in both FUT Minna and IBBU Lapai Nigeria, because research was carried out in Universities within Niger State. Research instrument (questionnaire) were given 120 university biology education students randomly selected to filled, also gender was considered as moderating variable. The questionnaire was administered on the students within two weeks of the study. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer research questions and ANOVA was used to analyze research hypotheses.

A. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

1. What is the mean of awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?
2. What is the mean of readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?
3. What are the mean differences of male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?
4. What are the mean differences of male and female readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?

B. RESEARCH HYPOTHESES

- H₀₁** There is no significant differences in the mean of male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State.
- H₀₂** There is no significant difference in the mean of readiness male and female universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of mean and standard deviation of awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for Biology in Niger State are below.

Research Question One: What is the mean of awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?

TABLE 1: Mean and Standard Deviation of Awareness of Universities Students Towards Utilization of Social Media for Educational Activities in Niger State

S/N	ITEMS	N	\bar{X}	SD	DECISION
Q1	Am aware that social media for instructional delivery is vital tool in biology education	120	3.64	1.11	Agree
Q2	Am aware WhatsApp as social media platform can be used for biology instruction in the school.	120	3.99	1.05	Agree
Q3	Am aware Zoom application as social media platform can be used for biology instructional d in the school.	120	3.71	1.25	Agree
Q4	The use of social media for instructional delivery will create awareness to both students and lecturers of biology education.	120	3.51	1.33	Agree
Q5	Instruction on social media look ambiguous	120	1.87	1.22	Disagree
	Decision Mean	3.00			
Q1	Am aware that social media for instructional delivery is vital tool in biology education	120	3.64	1.11	Agree
Q2	Am aware WhatsApp as social media platform can be used for biology instruction in the school.	120	3.99	1.05	Agree
Q3	Am aware Zoom application as social media platform can be used for biology instructional d in the school.	120	3.71	1.25	Agree
Mean	261.5930	2.35 5072	6.973 381	39.71 393	

Table 1 shows the mean and standard deviation of mean awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for educational activities in Niger State. The respondents are in agreement with the items stated in the research instrument on mean awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for educational activities in Niger State. Also, the items mean rating which ranged between 3.51 and 3.99 are all considered accepted based on the decision mean of 3.0 except item five. The implication is that, the awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for educational activities in Niger State is favourable since four items out five on mean awareness of universities students

towards utilization of social media for educational activities in Niger State show agreed based on decision mean.

What is the mean of readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?

TABLE 2: Mean and Standard Deviation of Readiness of Universities Students Towards Utilization of Social Media

S/N	Items	N	\bar{X}	Sd	Decision
Q1	I can save and retrieve social media information on biology education in my phone	120	3.47	1.18	Agree
Q2	I have access to personal android phone for social media usage for biology education	120	3.73	1.41	Agree
Q3	I attend at least one training on how to make use of social media for teaching and learning in the school	120	3.97	1.06	Agree
Q4	I use social media platforms to send and receive biology educational instruction.	120	3.88	1.03	Agree
Q5	I use to participate actively when using social media for teaching and learning of biology	120	3.85	1.14	Agree
Decision Mean:		3.0			

Table 2 shows the mean and standard deviation of readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for educational activities in Niger State. The respondents are in agreement with the items stated in the research instrument on readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media. Also, the items mean rating which ranged between 3.47 and 3.97 are all considered accepted based on the decision mean of 3.0. The implication is that, the readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for educational activities in Niger State is favourable, since all items agree on readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media show agreed based on decision mean of 3.0.

Research Question Three: What are the mean differences of male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?

TABLE 3: Mean and Standard Deviation of Male and Female Awareness of Universities Students towards Utilization of Social Media for Biology Education in Niger State

Group	N	Mean	Sd
Male	73	20.99	3.45
Female	47	21.63	3.87

Table 3 shows mean of mean differences of male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State. Male had mean of $\bar{X} = 20.99$, $SD = 3.45$ and Female had mean of $\bar{X} = 21.63$, $SD = 3.87$. The mean of female was slightly higher than their male counterpart by 0.63. The implication is that, there is no disparity between mean of male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education

Research Question Four: What are the mean differences of male and female readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State?

TABLE 4: Mean Standard Deviation of Male and Female Readiness of Universities Students towards Utilization of Social Media for Biology Education in Niger State

Group	N	Mean	SD
Male	73	21.20	2.78
Female	47	20.28	4.32

Table 4 shows mean of male and female readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State. Male had mean of $\bar{X} = 21.20$, $SD = 2.78$ and Female had mean of $\bar{X} = 20.28$, $SD = 4.32$. The mean of male was slightly higher than their female counterpart by 0.92. The implication is that, there is little disparity between male and female readiness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State.

Hypothesis One: There is no significant difference in the mean of male and female awareness of students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State.

TABLE 5: Summary of ANOVA on Awareness of Universities Students towards Utilization of Social Media for Biology Education

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	44.311	1	44.311	3.62	0.06
Within Groups	1442.055	118	12.221		
Total	1486.367	119			

Table 5 shows the finding of the analysis of variance on male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education as shown in (Table 3) revealed a $F(1, 118) = F$ value 3.62 $p = 0.06$ With this finding, the hypothesis was retained because p-value of 0.06 on the table was greater than the pre-set level of significant of $p > 0.05$. This implies that there is no significant difference in the mean of male and female awareness of universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State.

Hypothesis Two: There is no significant difference in the mean of readiness male and female universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education in Niger State.

TABLE 6: Summary of ANOVA on Readiness Male and Female Universities Students towards Utilization of Social Media for Biology Education

	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Between Groups	1.408	1	1.408	0.144	0.71
Within Groups	1157.717	118	9.811		
Total	1159.125	119			

Table 6 shows the finding of the analysis of variance on readiness of male and female universities students towards utilization of social media for educational activities as shown in (Table 4) revealed a $F(1, 118) = F$ value 3.62 $p = 0.06$ With this finding, the hypothesis was accepted because p-value of 0.71 on the table was greater than the pre-set level of significant of $p > 0.05$. This implies that there is no significant difference in the readiness of male and female universities students towards utilization of social media for biology education. There was no significant difference in the mean of male and female awareness of university students towards utilization of social media for biology in Niger State. This is in support of findings of Venkataraman (2018) who carried out study on M-learning awareness of high school students. The result

indicates that there was no significant difference in the awareness of male and female high school students on M-learning. There was no significant difference in the readiness of male and female university students towards utilization of social media for biology education. This is in support of study of Muhammed and Okan (2018) who carried out study on the readiness levels of pre-service teachers towards mobile learning in classroom management. It was revealed that readiness level of the prospective teachers does not change depending on the gender and the students use the mobile technologies most in communication, studying, acquiring information and making plans.

IV. CONCLUSION

It can be concluded that the computer science students' awareness and readiness towards use of social media for learning is positive. The study reveals that social media can be used for learning of computer science by students in the universities in Niger State. Social media should be used as tools in universities in Niger State for biology instructional delivery in order to act as supplementary teaching and learning materials. Biology education students should be motivated in order to make use of social media for biology education instructional delivery in their academic activities.

REFERENCES

- Adediran, E. M. T & Kehinde, A. O. (2013). Gender and Internet Use Pattern of Pre-Service Teachers in a Nigerian College of Education, *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 4(15),151-158
- Adeyinka, A. A. (2010). Gender differences in mathematics achievement. *African Journal of Education Studies*, 3(1), 179-199.
- Chen, B., & Bryer, T. (2012). Investigating Instructional Strategies for Using Social Media in Formal and Informal Learning. *The International Review of Research in Open and Distance Learning*, 13(1), 87-104.
- Chinedu, N. (2008) Examined Senior Secondary Schools awareness and readiness in the use of ICT to learn Biological Science in Calabar Municipal Area Council. An Unpublished M.ed Thesis Submitted to the Department of Science Education, University of Uyo.
- Effiong A. A. & Odey E.O. (2013) Information and Communication Technology web-based tools and instructional delivery in secondary school in Calabar Education zone. *A Journal of Nigeria Association Educational media and Technology (NAEMT)*, 3(4), 72-85.
- Micheal, D. D., Henry, B., Franklin, G. A., Fidelis, Q., (2016). Effects of perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use and gender on social media adoption among university students in Ghana. *International Journal of Social Media and Interactive Learning Environment*. 10(31), 30-42.
- Muhammed, B. & Okan, S. (2018). Determining the readiness levels of pre-service teachers towards mobile learning in classroom management, *Journal of Educational Research and Reviews*, 13(10), 382-390.
- Nsofor, C. C. & Bello, A. (2015). Emerging trends in educational technology Ibadan:Evi-Cole Publishers.
- Rochas, C.J. (2011). Essentials of social work policy practice. In Capella university, DSW8002 *Advanced knowledge of social work (Wiley Custom Edition)* 5(1)-43 56.
- Sharon, B.C. (2012). Towards an alternative educational technology, *British Journal of Educational Technology*, (25) 120-131.
- Venkataraman, S. (2018). M - Learning awareness of high school students. *International Journal of Human Resource Management and Research (IJHRMR)*, 8(6), 217-222.